

LEACHING OF COPPER FROM WASTE OF THE ALMALYK MINING AND METALLURGICAL PLANT

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Abstract

In this work, associations of bacteria from the dumps of oxidized and sulfide ores and flotation tailings of the copper processing plant of the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combine were studied for the ability to leach copper from these sources. It is shown that the association obtained from a mixture of associations of these three sources is the most active.

Keywords: *copper bioleaching, oxidized ores, sulfide ores, flotation tailings, chemolithotrophic microorganisms.*

Introduction. In the Almalyk ore field, as in the ores of most industrial deposits, copper is present in sulfide (CuS, Cu₂S, CuFeS₂, etc.) and oxidized (CuO, CuO•SiO₂, CuCO₃, CuSO₄) forms. When mining ore in open pits, the copper content in the ore rarely exceeds 1% (10 kg/t). When the copper content in the ore is from 0.3% to 1.0%, the ore is crushed to a size of 0.5-0.05 mm, enriched by flotation to 10-35%, and then blister copper is smelted from this concentrate. Flotation waste from a copper processing plant, which contains less than 0.1% copper, is stored in tailings ponds. If copper in the ore is less than 0.3%, this ore is stored in off-balance ore dumps. For more than 70 years, more than one and a half billion tons of technogenic waste, containing in addition to copper, gold and silver, also a number of rare earth metals and elements, have accumulated in the dumps of off-balance ore and tailings of the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combine (AMMC). They contain more than \$20 billion worth of copper and gold alone. And this is not counting other noble and rare earth metals and elements. Moreover, the most copper is found in 1,350 million tons of flotation waste from a copper processing plant (COP) with a copper content of 0.10-0.12%, gold - 0.2-0.4 g t⁻¹ [3, p.17].

To obtain copper and other valuable metals from these wastes, the most economically acceptable technology is heap leaching. It is based on the fact that a heap containing several million tons of ore is built from off-balance ores and flotation waste. A solution of sulfuric acid is applied to the top of the heap. It permeates the heap, dissolves the copper contained in the ore and flows out from the bottom of the heap in the form of solutions of copper sulfate and other metals. These solutions are collected, the metals are separated from them, and the sulfuric acid solution is again fed to the top of the pile. Up to 20% of all copper in the world is obtained by this leaching method [4, p.205].

In ores containing metal sulfides, the bacteria *Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans* and some others were found, which oxidize insoluble metal sulfides to form soluble metal sulfates [5, p.112]. If special favorable

conditions are created for these bacteria, then the bacterial oxidation of metal sulfides can be hundreds and thousands of times faster than chemical oxidation [7, p.270]. Based on this, various biohydrometallurgical technologies for bioleaching of metals began to develop. The purpose of this work was to select bacterial associations from the ores of the Almalyk MMC for the ability to leach copper from the flotation waste of a copper processing plant (CPP).

Materials and methods. The work used a sample of sulfide ores from dump No. 8 (after crushing, particle size 2-5 mm), oxidized ores from dump No. 39 (after crushing, particle size 3-10 mm) and a sample of flotation waste from tailings dump No. 1 (particle size 0.5-0.05 mm). The number of bacteria in these samples was determined in a series of limiting tenfold dilutions on Silverman-Landgren 9K nutrient medium for *Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans* and Waksman medium for *Acidithiobacillus thiooxidans*, in sixfold repetition. The titer was calculated using McCready tables [2, p.68]. Identification of strains of microorganisms *Acidithiobacillus ferrooxidans* and *Acidithiobacillus thiooxidans* was carried out on the basis of the key given in the identification of bacteria [1, p.57].

Cultivation of microorganisms was carried out on a shaker (180 rpm) at 28-32° C, pH - 1.6-2.0, at different ratios of solid and liquid phases (S:L). Modeling of processes of biological leaching of ores was carried out in columns with a diameter of 8.5 cm with 1.0 kg of ore in each. 1 kg of ore was poured dry into the column (sectional area 56.7 cm²). In this case, the height of the ore layer was 12-14 cm. Then the ore was wetted and acidified with tap water, acidified with sulfuric acid to pH 1.5-2.0, passing the solution from the top of the column through the mass of ore. The pH of the solution, after passing through the ore, was determined, the solution was again acidified with sulfuric acid to pH 1.4-1.5 and again passed through the column. This process was carried out until the pH value in the leaching solution at the outlet was reduced to 2.5-2.0. In this case, the acidification of the ore occurred in 16-20 cycles. During the acidification process, the moisture capacity of

the ore was determined: dump No. 39 - $0.19 \text{ l}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, dump No. 8 - $0.21 \text{ l}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, tailings dump No. 1 - $0.19 \text{ l}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, permeability: No. 39 - $11.2 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{hour}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, No.8 - $9.8 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{hour}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, XX No.1 - $13.6 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{hour}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and sulfuric acid consumption : No. 39 - $5.7 \text{ g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, No. 8 - $15.5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, XX No. 1 - $16.6 \text{ g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$.

After the columns were acidified, 0.5 L of a bacterial suspension in Silverman-Landgren 9K medium with a concentration of $10^6 \text{ cells ml}^{-1}$ was applied to them, and after each cycle the content of copper and iron (II) and (III) in the percolation solution was determined. The determination of copper ions was carried out by the voltammetric method using an ABC-5 voltammetric analyzer. Voltmetrics (Russia) according to the manufacturer's methods. The concentration of oxide and ferrous iron in the solution was determined by the complexometric method with a solution of Trilon B.

Results and its discussion. It is known that industrial bioleaching processes are carried out not by pure cultures, but by associations of microorganisms. At the same time, the best oxidation results, as a rule, can be achieved using microbial associations adapted to specific mineral raw materials [6; 4, p.206]. To select the most effective association of bacteria oxidizing AMMC waste, samples were taken from dumps of off-balance oxidized and sulfide ores and MOP waste from tailings pond No. 1. From the ore samples from each dump, 3 samples of 10 g each were taken and placed in vials with 100 ml of sterile water and mixed vigorously. The pH of these samples was measured and the number of iron-oxidizing bacteria in Silverman-Landgren 9K medium and sulfur-oxidizing bacteria in Waxman medium was determined using a series of limiting dilutions. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

The number of iron-oxidizing bacteria in Silverman-Landgren 9K medium and sulfur-oxidizing bacteria in Waksman medium in various ore samples at pH = 2.0.

Source ore	Sample No.	pH hoods	Number of iron-oxidizing bacteria per 1 g of ore	Number of sulfur-oxidizing bacteria per 1 g of ore
Dump No. 8 Sulfide.	8-1	9,2	$5,0 \cdot 10^0$	$6,0 \cdot 10^0$
	8-2	8,8	$1,0 \cdot 10^1$	$1,3 \cdot 10^1$
	8-3	8,7	$1,3 \cdot 10^1$	$1,3 \cdot 10^1$
Dump No. 39 Oxidized.	39-1	6,0	$1,0 \cdot 10^2$	$2,5 \cdot 10^2$
	39-2	6,9	$2,5 \cdot 10^1$	$1,3 \cdot 10^2$
	39-3	6,7	$6,0 \cdot 10^1$	$6,0 \cdot 10^2$
Tailings pond No. 1 Mixed.	TP-1	8,7	$2,5 \cdot 10^2$	$1,5 \cdot 10^0$
	TP-2	8,6	$6,0 \cdot 10^1$	$2,3 \cdot 10^0$
	TP-3	8,6	$1,0 \cdot 10^2$	$6,0 \cdot 10^0$

The table shows that aqueous extracts from oxidized ores are weakly acidic, and those from sulfide ores and tailings are weakly alkaline. Since we took ore samples from the dry surface of the deposits, the number of iron- and sulfur-oxidizing bacteria of interest to us was low: from a few to hundreds per 1 g of ore. To increase the number of these bacteria to a concentration sufficient for microbial bioleaching ($\approx 10^6 \text{ cells ml}^{-1}$),

they were cumulatively cultivated in Silverman-Landgren and Waksman media pH = 2.0 on a shaker at 180 rpm-1 or when bubbling with excess air, with a ratio of solid phase to liquid T:L = 1:10. The activity of these associations was tested by leaching copper from 100 g of pyrite concentrate acidified to pH = 2.0 on a shaker at 180 rpm for 5 days at a solid to liquid volume ratio of T:L = 1:10 in Silverman-Landgren medium 9K. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

The ability of various associations of microorganisms with a cell concentration of 10^6 ml^{-1} in Silverman-Landgren 9K medium to leach copper from pyrite concentrate.

Source of bacteria association	Oxidative iron activity, $\text{mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1} \cdot \text{hour}^{-1}$	Copper concentration per 5 days, $\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$
Dump No. 39 of oxidized ores	51,0	0,44
Dump No. 8 of sulfide ores	82,0	0,72
Tailings pond No. 1	48,0	0,42
Dump No. 39 + Dump No. 8 + TP No. 1	97,0	0,88

The table shows that individually the most active association is from the sulfide ore dump, but a mixture of associations from three sources is even more active. In this regard, all subsequent experiments on copper leaching from flotation tailings were carried out using a mixture of associations. The species composition of the acidophilic mixture of associations was studied. The predominance of *A. ferrooxidans* was shown, as well as the presence of *A. thiooxidans*, *Leptospirillum ferrooxidans* and *Sulfobacillus thermosulfidooxidans*. Next, the ability of the resulting mixture of associations

to leach copper from samples of oxidized and sulfide ore and flotation tailings was studied by simulating heap leaching on columns with a diameter of 8 cm from 1 kg of ore. The columns were pre-acidified with sulfuric acid to pH=2.0 and leaching was carried out with a combined association of microorganisms with a cell concentration of about 10^6 ml^{-1} in Silverman-Landgren 9K medium. The volume of the percolation solution is 0.5 l. The solution supplied from above was bubbled with excess air. The results of these experiments are presented in Table 3.

Table 3

Copper yield during bacterial leaching with a cell concentration of about $10^6 \cdot \text{ml}^{-1}$ from columns with 1 kg of ore from three sources in Silverman-Landgren 9K medium. The volume of the percolation solution is 0.5L

Source ore	Copper content in ore, according to the AMMC act, $\text{g} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$	Average time of one cycle, min	Number of cycles	Copper concentration in the percolation solution $\text{g} \cdot \text{l}^{-1}$. Average of 4 columns \pm	Copper yield from 1 kg of ore, g (%) of the ore content
Dump No. 39 of oxidized ores	8,0 (0,80%)	68 \pm 16	25	0,72 \pm 0,81	0,36 (4,3%)
			30	0,94 \pm 0,12	0,47 (5,6%)
			40	1,05 \pm 0,15	0,52 (6,2%)
Dump No. 39 of oxidized ores	2,0 (0,20%)	85 \pm 18	25	0,84 \pm 0,08	0,42 (20%)
			30	0,91 \pm 0,12	0,45 (22,5%)
			40	1,13 \pm 0,13	0,56 (27,5%)
Dump No. 39 of oxidized ores	1,2 (0,12%)	40 \pm 12	25	0,24 \pm 0,03	0,12 (2,3%)
			30	0,32 \pm 0,05	0,16 (12,2%)
			40	0,42 \pm 0,06	0,21 (16,6%)

The table shows that copper leaching from different sources occurs at different rates. So, after the 40th cycle, 27.5% of the total copper contained in it is leached from sulfide ore, 16.6% of copper is leached from flotation tailings, and only 6.2% of copper is leached from oxidized ore. The work was carried out with the support of Contract No. ALM-202110123 of the Agency for Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Conclusion. An association of bacteria was isolated from a mixture of oxidized and sulfide ores and flotation tailings of the Almalyk MMC, which can be used to leaching copper from the wastes of the Almalyk MMC.

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